

ASURS

Applied Sciences
Undergraduate Research Sessions

2024

ABSTRACTS

Organized by
Faculty of Applied Sciences
Rajarata University of Sri Lanka

Applied Sciences Undergraduate Research Sessions

ASURS 2024

13th March 2024

Faculty of Applied Sciences
Rajarata University of Sri Lanka

Contents

Message from the Vice Chancellor	i
Message from the Dean	ii
Message from the Programme Chair	iii
Profile of Keynote Speaker	iv
Abstract of Keynote Speech	v
Presentation Evaluation Panel	vi
Poster Evaluation Panel	viii
List of Abstracts	ix
Abstracts	1
Biology	1
Chemistry	12
Computing	23
Health Promotion	39
Mathematics	45
Physics	56
List of Posters	63
Organization of ASURS 2023	66

Message from the Vice Chancellor

With great pleasure, I offer my congratulations as the Faculty of Applied Sciences prepares to launch its sixth Applied Sciences Undergraduate Research Sessions (ASURS) in 2024.

Research has always been a top priority for the Rajarata University of Sri Lanka and has been essential to its academic advancement. The institution has created an atmosphere that promotes systematic research, intellectual engagements, and greater dissemination of diverse areas of study by fostering innovation and improving society. As a result, there is a culture in academia that encourages the pursuit of knowledge for the good of all and supports critical inquiry.

Given that the Faculty of Applied Sciences includes alumni who rank among the top 2% of researchers worldwide, I have every faith in them. Undergraduate research is a vital component of education that fosters students' interest and enthusiasm for the academic goal. The various viewpoints and areas of competence that the disciplines of Physics, Mathematics, Health Promotion, Computing, Chemistry, and Biology brought to ASURS 2024 are not only evidence of the faculty's strength but also a step in the right direction toward a more enlightened future. I value the dedication and hard work of students as well as the guidance provided by academic personnel when undertaking research. The department has made it a practice to give student research participants the chance to present their findings in a scientific setting. Additionally, I urge undergrads to disseminate their research not just among their peers but also with the general public, since this will enable them to have a more significant influence on society.

I am grateful to the faculty staff, the dean, and the ASURS 2024 organizing team for their commitment and perseverance in making this year's research sessions a success. Through collaborative efforts, the faculty has enhanced the university's research culture and added to the overall richness of the academic environment.

I would like to extend my congratulations to every one of the undergraduates who are presenting at ASURS 2024 and wish them all a successful and enjoyable research session.

Professor (Mrs) G.A.S. Ginigaddara
Vice Chancellor
Rajarata University of Sri Lanka
Mihintale

Message from the Dean

I am pleased to extend this message to celebrate the Applied Sciences Undergraduate Research Sessions 2024 (ASURS 2024). The Faculty of Applied Sciences is renowned for its research excellence, exploring various fields and continuously pushing the limits of knowledge. Our efforts over the years have been globally recognized, with our alumni consistently ranked among the top 2% of researchers worldwide by the prestigious Stanford University rankings. This is a testament to the dedication and innovation that define our academic community.

Our research covers a wide range of topics, from studying the smallest molecules to complex animals and human beings. We explore everything from the nature of chemicals to the behavior of human beings and work on producing products for human consumption as well as finding ways to improve human well-being. Our research also includes discovering IT solutions and developing mathematical models that can help advance mankind. ASURS is a platform created to support the next generation of researchers by providing them with an opportunity to share their undergraduate research with the wider research community.

ASURS 2024 is the culmination of our efforts, providing a platform for our young researchers to showcase their undergraduate projects to a wider audience. With 87 oral presentations and 32 poster presentations covering all five departments of the faculty, this event promises to be a celebration of scholarly inquiry and intellectual curiosity. I am particularly pleased to note the introduction of a pre-conference session, as well as the inclusion of engaging activities such as the 3 MT thesis presentation competition and an Art competition, which will undoubtedly enhance the research experience for our students.

I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to the Organizing Committee of ASURS 2024 for their tireless efforts in bringing this event to fruition within a short timeframe. Their dedication and meticulous planning have been instrumental in ensuring the success of this endeavor. Additionally, I extend my thanks to the academic staff members of the faculty for their invaluable guidance and mentorship, which has played a pivotal role in nurturing the talents of our students. To all the students presenting their findings today, I offer my heartfelt congratulations. Your participation in this event marks the beginning of what I am confident will be a journey filled with discovery, innovation, and impact. May you seize this opportunity as a stepping stone towards your future research endeavors, and may your passion for knowledge continue to inspire others in the pursuit of excellence.

Dr Manoj Fernando
Dean

Message from the Programme Chair

On behalf of the organizing committee, I am pleased to welcome you to the 06th Applied Sciences Undergraduate Research Sessions (ASURS) 2024 organized by the Faculty of Applied Sciences, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka. It has been a great honor and privilege to serve as the Chair of ASURS 2024.

The main objective of ASURS is to provide our final year (both fourth year and third year) undergraduate students with a professional and academic conference platform to present their research findings in aid of initiation of their research careers. This year ASURS portrays high quality research work carried out by our undergraduates under the guidance of their supervisors in the field of Biology, Chemistry, Computing, Health promotion, Mathematics and Physics. The Faculty offers both Bachelor of Science and Bachelor of Science Honors degrees and the general degree programme feature an elective research component with 2-3 credits. ASURS provides a platform for both these students as this time we are proud to announce the participation of eighty seven students those of whom which thirty two are students following general degree programme and shall involve with poster presentations. Aligned with ASURS, several parallel programmes are organized to offer students with opportunities for excellence across diverse fields. For the second time 3MT completion was organized and twenty five presenters participated. For the first time, ASURS is incorporated with pre-conference sessions organized in collaboration with several student associations attached to departments to promote the theme “from students to student”.

This event may have not been possible, if not for the cooperation rendered by Prof. Sanjeewanie Ginigaddara, the Vice Chancellor of the Rajarata University of Sri Lanka. I cannot forget the guidance and cooperation given to us by the Dean of the Faculty of Applied Sciences, Dr. Manoj Fernando. Moreover, I take this opportunity to thank all the Heads of the Department, Assistant Registrar and the team, Assistant Bursa and the team and non-presenting students of the Faculty of Applied Sciences for their support in making this event a success. I would also like to thank the evaluation panels and special guests who attend despite their busy schedules to grace this event. Further, my sincere thanks go to the students and their supervisors for contributing their work to ASURS 2024 and would like to congratulate all the presenters. I thank my editorial board and the organizing committee who took the challenge of organizing this event with a very short notice. A special thanks goes to our sponsor Bank of Ceylon who provided us with financial support.

Dear presenters, may this be a remarkable beginning of your research careers.

Dr. Dilani K. Hettiarachchi
Programme Chair
ASURS 2024

Profile of the Keynote Speaker - Professor Kosala Weerakoon

Professor Kosala Weerakoon is a well-accomplished scholar and educator currently serving as a Professor in Medical Parasitology, Faculty of Medicine and Allied Sciences (FMAS), Rajarata University of Sri Lanka (RUSL). As a young scientist making remarkable strides in his field of expertise, Prof. Weerakoon is an influential figure with an impressive academic background and a proven track record of outstanding research.

He holds a Ph.D in Parasitology from the University of Queensland, and QIMR Berghofer Medical Research Institute, Brisbane, Australia, where his research focused on tropical infections and novel diagnostics. With over one decade of professional experience, Prof. Weerakoon has held key positions in academia. He served as the Head of the Department of Parasitology, FMAS, RUSL, and currently, he is a Visiting-Scientist at QIMR-Berghofer Medical Research Institute, Brisbane, Australia, a Visiting-Lecturer at the Faculty of Medicine, Wayamba University of Sri Lanka, and a fellow of the Royal College of Physicians, Edinburgh, UK. This invaluable experience has fortified his interdisciplinary research approach to drive meaningful advancements in the field of tropical infectious diseases.

Throughout his career, Professor Weerakoon has been honoured with multiple prestigious awards, scholarships, and research grants, highlighting his exceptional contributions to the scientific community. His expertise in the field of tropical infectious diseases has resulted over 60 journal publications in esteemed peer-reviewed scientific journals, with over 1800 citations from fellow researchers worldwide.

In addition to his recent research that focuses on the development of novel molecular tools to improve the diagnosis of many tropical infectious diseases, he is a passionate advocate for public engagement and scientific outreach. He has consistently sought opportunities to communicate his research findings to wider audiences, fostering a greater understanding and appreciation for the field of parasitology.

Abstract of the Keynote Speech by Professor Kosala Weerakoon

Ideas into Reality: Bridging Research, Policy, and Practice

Bridging the gap between research, policy, and practice is crucial for driving substantial societal change, particularly in the developing world. This process involves translating theoretical knowledge and realistic findings into actionable policies and interventions to address key needs of the modern world. Collaboration, communication, and commitment across disciplines and stakeholders are essential for this journey from ideas to implementation.

Research is the key to generating evidence-based insights, and it must translate into implementable policies to guide resource allocation and intervention frameworks at various levels. The transition from policy formulation to implementation faces challenges such as bureaucratic hurdles, competing interests, and resource limitations. Practice becomes crucial here, involving efforts to translate policies into tangible actions that engage communities and adapt to local contexts.

Hence, successful bridging requires active collaboration among researchers, policymakers, practitioners, and the public. Equity, diversity, and inclusion are vital, ensuring policies and practices address the needs of communities, particularly in developing settings. Rigorous efforts are needed to bridge the gap between research, policy, and practice in the developing world. This interdisciplinary approach holds the key to making meaningful differences in individuals' and communities' lives.

Members of the Presentation Evaluation Panel

Biology

Dr Rasanie E. Padmathilake, Department of Plant Sciences, Faculty of Agriculture, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka, Puliyankulama, Anuradhapura

Dr N.P.S. Kumburegama, Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, University of Peradeniya, Peradeniya

Dr Prasad Tharanga Jayasooriya, Department of Bioprocess Technology, Faculty of Technology, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka, Mihintale

Chemistry

Professor Rohan Weerasooriya, Division for Environment Sciences, National Institute of Fundamental Studies, Kandy

Dr Kumudika G. Jayalath, Department of Chemistry, Open University of Sri Lanka, Anuradhapura Regional Centre, Anuradhapura

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Dr Tharani D. Fernando, Department of Bioprocess Technology, Faculty of Technology, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka, Mihintale

Computing

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Dr H.M.B.P. Ranaweera, Department of Information Systems, Faculty of Management Studies, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka, Mihintale

Mr P.S. Palliyaguruge, Department of Computing, Faculty of Applied Sciences, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka, Mihintale

Health Promotion

Professor Kosala Weerakoon, Department of Parasitology, Faculty of Medicine and Allied Sciences, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka, Saliyapura, Anuradhapura

Professor N.K. Anjana Silva, Department of Parasitology, Faculty of Medicine and Allied Sciences, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka, Saliyapura, Anuradhapura

Dr Shobha Gunathilaka, Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Medicine and Allied Sciences, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka, Saliyapura, Anuradhapura

Mathematics

Professor W.B. Daundasekera, Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science, University of Peradeniya, Peradeniya

Dr M. Kayanan, Senior Lecturer, Department of Physical Science, Faculty of Applied Science, University of Vavuniya, Pambaimadu, Vavuniya

Dr T.H.K.R. De Silva, Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science, University of Peradeniya, Peradeniya

Physics

Professor T.M.W.J. Bandara, Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, University of Peradeniya, Peradeniya,

Dr Lakmal Jayarathne, Division for Environment Sciences, National Institute of Fundamental Studies, Hanthana Road, Kandy

Mr S. Kuhanesan, Department of Physical Science, Faculty of Applied Science, University of Vavuniya, Vauniya

Dr L. Jayasuriya, Department of Electrical and Electronic Technology, Faculty of Technology, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka, Mihintale

Members of the Poster Evaluation Panel

Biology

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Physics

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Dr L. Jayasuriya, Department of Electrical and Electronic Technology, Faculty of Technology, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka, Mihintale

List of Abstracts

BIOLOGY

INVESTIGATION OF ANTI-INFLAMMATORY EFFECT OF SELECTED PLANT EXTRACTS AGAINST *Escherichia coli* INDUCED SEPTIC SHOCK IN ZEBRAFISH MODEL

ISOLATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF THERMOPHILIC BACTERIA FROM GOMARANKADAWALA AND KANNIYA HOT WATER SPRINGS IN SRI LANKA FOR FUTURE BIOTECHNOLOGICAL APPLICATIONS

DEVELOPMENT AND QUALITY ASSURANCE OF A PROBIOTIC CEREAL BAR

THE IMPACT OF SOME BACTERIAL AND FUNGAL BIO-FERTILIZERS ON THE ROOT ENDOPHYTIC FUNGAL POPULATION AND GROWTH OF RICE (*Oryza sativa* L.)

EVALUATION OF CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND ANTIBIOTIC ACTIVITY OF SELECTED LICHEN SPECIES FROM MIHINTALE, SRI LANKA AGAINST FOOD-BORNE PATHOGENIC BACTERIA

EVALUATION OF ENTOMOPATHOGENIC FUNGI IN BIOCONTROL OF SMALL HIVE BEETLE (*Aethina tumida*)

IN-VITRO SCREENING OF *Punica granatum* BREEDING LINES FOR ANTHRACNOSE DISEASE RESISTANCE BY DETACHED LEAF INOCULATION TECHNIQUE

FURTHER INVESTIGATION INTO THE MOLECULAR PHYLOGENETICS OF THE SRI LANKAN LAND-SNAIL GENUS *Corilla*

SOCIAL BEHAVIOUR OF *Semnopithecus vetulus* IN HETEROSPECIFIC AND CONSPECIFIC GROUPS

EXPLORING RESOURCE PARTITIONING AMONG AVIFAUNA IN DAMBULLA KALUDIYAPOKUNA FOREST

CHEMISTRY

PHYTOCHEMICAL PROFILING AND BIOCHEMICAL ACTIVITIES OF *Diplodiscus verrucosus* AND *Dimorphocalyx glabellus*

STUDY AND FORMULATION OF STARCH-CELLULOSE ACETATE BIODEGRADABLE POLYMER COMPOSITE

STARCH-BASED POLYMER COMPOSITES USING TEAK WOOD DUST AND COCOA HUSK POWDER AS REINFORCED FILLERS

OPTIMIZING ELECTROCOAGULATION PROCESSES THROUGH VARIABLE FREQUENCY AC CURRENT AND ELECTRODE CONFIGURATIONS

ZIRCON ($ZrSiO_4$) MODIFIED POLYANILINE COMPOSITE FOR ALUMINIUM REMOVAL IN WATER

PHYSIOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF CROSS-LINKED CASSAVA STARCH POLYMER WITH TRISODIUM PHOSPHATE

EXPLORING THE BIOACTIVITY, CHEMICAL PROFILING AND THE ASSESSMENT OF TRACE METAL CONTAMINATION IN MARINE SPONGES

ISOLATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF DISSOLVED ORGANIC CARBON IN THURUWILA WATER

SQUARE WAVE PULSE VOLTAMMETRY FOR THE QUANTIFICATION OF ANTIBIOTICS, CIPROFLOXACIN IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

PREPARATION OF NANOCELLULOSE REINFORCED CASSAVA STARCH BASED BIODEGRADABLE POLYMER COMPOSITES

COMPUTING

AUTOMATED SYSTEM FOR DETECTING ROTATION RULE VIOLATION REGARDING PLAYERS' POSITION IN VOLLEYBALL

A NEW MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH FOR IN-GAME BEHAVIOR ANALYSIS OF FOOTBALL PLAYERS BASED ON PLAYER STATISTICS

IDENTIFICATION OF NITROGEN (N), PHOSPHORUS (P), AND POTASSIUM (K) DEFICIENCIES IN RICE CROP USING IMAGE PROCESSING

IMPROVING PERFORMANCE OF IMAGE PREPROCESSING FOR EFFICIENT IRIS RECOGNITION

COLOR AND THEME BASED OPTIMAL OBJECT PLACING FOR BUILDING INTERIOR USING AUGMENTED REALITY

DEVELOPING AN AI-POWERED CHATBOT TO ASSIST UNDERGRADUATES IN OVERCOMING EXAM STRESS

GRAYSCALE IMAGE COLORIZATION USING MACHINE LEARNING

DRIVER DROWSINESS DETECTION USING IMAGE PROCESSING AND ENSEMBLE LEARNING

PREDICTING POPULARITY IN SINHALA YOUTUBE VIDEOS USING MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS

AN APPROACH FOR PREDICTION OF BLACK PEPPER (*Piper nigrum L.*) CROP PRODUCTIVITY BASED ON WEATHER PARAMETERS USING MACHINE LEARNING

DETECTION OF SINHALA TEXT BASED CYBER-BULLYING USING ONTOLOGY ENGINEERING AND MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES

ENHANCING CRYPTOCURRENCY PRICE PREDICTIONS WITH MACHINE LEARNING

A NOVEL MACHINE LEARNING MODEL FOR EMOTION RECOGNITION IN SINHALA LANGUAGE SOCIAL MEDIA POSTS ANALYZING TEXT AND EMOTICONS

WASTE COLLECTING FLOATING ROBOT FOR STILL WATER BODIES USING OPTIMAL PATH IN REAL-TIME

MACHINE LEARNING AND LEXICON-BASED HYBRID SENTIMENT ANALYSIS APPROACH FOR MOVIE REVIEWS

HEALTH PROMOTION

CHANGING FOOD HABITS OF ADOLESCENTS BY ADDRESSING DETERMINANTS OF FOOD HABITS USING HEALTH PROMOTION APPROACH IN SELECTED SCHOOLS IN GALENBINDUNUWEWA

CHANGING THE KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES, AND PRACTICES REGARDING SMOKELESS TOBACCO (SLT) USE AMONG ADULT FACTORY WORKERS IN ANURADHAPURA USING THE HEALTH PROMOTION APPROACH

EFFECTIVENESS OF A HEALTH PROMOTION INTERVENTION TO REDUCE PHYSICAL BULLYING AMONG ADOLESCENTS IN TERMS OF CHANGES IN THE KNOWLEDGE, PRACTICES AND ATTITUDES OF ADOLESCENTS TOWARDS BULLYING IN A/AL- NOOR MAHA VIDYALAYA, IKKIRIGOLLEWA, ANURADHAPURA DISTRICT

EFFECTIVENESS OF A HEALTH PROMOTION INTERVENTION TO REDUCE THE RISKS OF UNINTENTIONAL HOME INJURIES BY IMPROVING HOME ENVIRONMENT IN RURAL VILLAGES OF ANURADHAPURA DISTRICT

EFFECTIVENESS OF A HEALTH PROMOTION INTERVENTION DESIGNED TO IMPROVE SELECTED ASPECTS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL WELLBEING OF SCHOOL-GOING ADOLESCENTS IN ANURADHAPURA DISTRICT

MATHEMATICS

A SPATIO-TEMPORAL ANALYSIS OF DENGUE EPIDEMICS IN SRI LANKA AT THE PROVINCIAL LEVEL

THE INCIDENCE COLOURING FOR HONEYCOMB GRAPHS & INCIDENCE COLOURING APPLICATION

BEES ALGORITHM FOR SOLVING TRANSPORTATION PROBLEM

RAINBOW CONNECTION NUMBER OF SPECIAL TYPE OF GRAPHS

ENHANCE THE PREDICTION PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MARKET USING CLUSTERING TECHNIQUES

A NOVEL HEURISTIC APPROACH TO THE ONE-DIMENSIONAL BIN PACKING PROBLEM

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF TWO-PHASE HEURISTIC ALGORITHMS TO SOLVE THE MULTI-DEPOT TRAVELLING SALESMAN PROBLEM

A NEW THIRD-ORDER APPROXIMATION FOR THE FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES

TOURIST ARRIVAL FORECASTING IN SRI LANKA AMIDST COVID-19 USING DEEP LEARNING AND MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH

FORECASTING MISSING DATA IN ADULT-CENSUS BIG DATA USING MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS

PHYSICS

WATER SPLITTING BY CARBON (C), NITROGEN (N) AND CHROMIUM (Cr) DOPED TITANIUM DIOXIDE (TiO₂)

AN ALGORITHM FOR TWO-DIMENSIONAL MODELLING OF THE SEDIMENT DISTRIBUTION IN SEDIMENTARY BASINS INTERPRETING SATELLITE GRAVITY ANOMALIES

QUANTITATIVE CHARACTERIZATION OF SUB SURFACE WATER QUALITY BY USING ADVANCED ELECTRICAL RESISTIVITY IMAGING AND INVERSE MODELING TECHNIQUES

DEVELOPMENT OF ACTIVATED COCONUT SHELL CHARCOAL AND CARBON NANOTUBES COMPOSITE AS COUNTER ELECTRODE FOR DYE-SENSITIZED SOLAR CELL APPLICATIONS

INTERPRETATION OF SATELLITE GRAVITY ANOMALIES TO ESTIMATE THE CONTINENTAL CRUST - OCEANIC CRUST BOUNDARY OVER THE EASTERN PART OF SRI LANKA

DEVELOPMENT OF PVDF POLYMER-BASED GEL POLYMER ELECTROLYTE FOR LITHIUM-ION BATTERIES

CHEMISTRY

OPTIMIZING ELECTROCOAGULATION PROCESSES THROUGH VARIABLE FREQUENCY AC CURRENT AND ELECTRODE CONFIGURATIONS

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Electrocoagulation (EC) can be defined as the electrochemical involvement of waste water treatment and an eco-friendly approach. In the traditional approach, direct current was employed to produce coagulants, polymetallic hydroxide species, by electrodisolution of metal electrodes such as aluminium (Al) and iron (Fe). Compared to other waste water treatment processes, the EC is a cost-effective method. However, the traditional electrocoagulation process that was conducted with direct current (DC) associates with certain drawbacks such as deposition of non-conducting material on the anode and passivation limits. The application of alternative current (AC) has been found to be a highly effective method to overcome the drawbacks of DCEC, and minimizes the higher electrode dissolution and minimize nonconducting material deposition by alternating the polarity of electrodes. In this study, current density, applied potential, frequency of current, initial pH, initial conductivity of electrolyte, temperature, operational time, electrolyte composition, electrode material, and configuration were studied for efficient removal of Ca and Mg in water. It was found that, the final pH of treated water depends on the initial composition of the electrolyte in the wastewater. Under optimal conditions of 14.00 volts, 300 Hz AC, and 90 minutes, with Al-Al electrode system, a removal of 80% Ca²⁺ and 70% of Mg²⁺ were achieved. EC carried out for 1000 μS/cm Na₂SO₄ and 1000 μS/cm CaCl₂ + Mg(NO₃)₂ solutions, the final pH value reached approximately to 10.04, with the Na₂SO₄ electrolyte and 8.34 with the CaCl₂ + Mg(NO₃)₂ electrolyte. For other Al-Fe, and Fe-Fe electrode configurations, different efficiencies were investigated.

Keywords: *Electrocoagulation, Electrodissolution, Polymetallic hydroxide, Coagulants, Alternative current*